

127 kg available NPK/ha. Farmyard manure (FYM) (0.562% N, 0.13% P, 0.75% K) was applied on a dry weight basis at 5 t/ha as an organic source for the main field only. Azospirillum was applied as a biofertilizer at 2 kg/800 m² of nursery area and at 2 kg/ha for the main field. P and K were applied,

per soil test recommendation, at 2.2 and 120 kg/ha, respectively, uniformly to all plots. N at four levels (see table) was applied as 50% basal and the remainder in equal splits at active tillering and panicle initiation.

The effect on yield of biofertilizer and organic manure either individually or in

combination was not significant, but in the subplots, N level was significant. N applied per soil test recommendation (98 kg N/ha) recorded significantly higher grain yield (4.3 t/ha) than the other treatments (see table) and a 30% yield increase over the control (3.3 t/ha). □

Sodicity-induced morphological disorder in rice laminae

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Soils having pH 7.4, 9.4, 9.8, and 10.0 were achieved by saturating sieved dry soil of pH 7.4 with different concentrations of sodium bicarbonate solution. The saturated soil was

subjected to repeated cycles of drying and wetting for 2 mo and then potted.

We planted 35-d-old seedlings of rice variety T3 in the pots. About 30 d after transplanting, white bands started appearing in the upper 1/3 portion of the first to third laminae from the top in plants growing at pH 10.0 (see figure). The white portion collapsed and the affected part withered. The symptoms were minor in some tillers at pH 9.8 and were not found at pH 7.4 and 9.4.

Laminae with symptoms at pH 10.0

were separated into 1/3 affected and 2/3 healthy parts. Laminae without symptoms at pH 7.4 were separated into upper 1/3 and lower 2/3 parts. Samples in three replications were analyzed for Na, K, Ca, and Mg content.

Laminae at pH 7.4 showed almost uniform Na content in upper 1/3 and lower 2/3 parts, but K content was more than double in the lower 2/3 (see table). Ca and Mg were higher in the upper part.

Laminae at pH 10.0 showed increased Na and Mg content, but K and Ca decreased. Distribution between the two parts was similar for Ca and Mg, but Na⁺ was less in the upper 1/3. K content did not show marked differences in the two parts. It is difficult to say whether such localized chlorosis, followed by withering, at higher sodicity is a cause or effect of marked change in distribution of K between the upper 1/3 and lower 2/3 of laminae. □

Healthy and chorotic laminae from rice plants growing at pH 7.4 and 10.0. CSSRI, Karnal, India.

Elemental composition of upper (U) 1/3 and lower (L) 2/3 of healthy and affected laminae of rice variety T3 growing in sodic and nonsodic soils. CSSRI, Karnal, India.

pH	Percent dry weight							
	Na		K		Ca		Mg	
	U1/3	L2/3	U1/3	L2/3	U1/3	L2/3	U1/3	L2/3
7.4	0.05	0.04	1.07	2.26	0.38	0.24	0.37	0.32
10.0	0.82	0.96	0.70	0.72	0.29	0.22	0.54	0.45

Effect of fineness and time of pyrites application on rice yield and alkali soil properties

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The efficiency of using pyrites to reclaim alkali soils depends upon sulfur transformation, which is influenced by the fineness of the pyrites and the time allowed for oxidation before mixing into the soil. We studied the effect of 3 degrees of fineness (<3, 3-5, and 5-10 mm) and 3 times (0, 1, and 2 wk before transplanting) of application. The experiment was a factorial randomized block design with four replications.